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The current state of saiga habitats in the North-Western pre-Caspian region

In the past decades, the North-West pre-Caspian saiga population has been extremely small. According to the survey conducted by WWF in 2020, it consisted of only about 6,350 individuals (otr-online.ru/news/krasnoknizhnyh-saygakov-poschitali-s-pomoshchyu-bespilotnikov-152138.html). The low number explained why saigas hardly made long-distance migrations, preferring to stay throughout the year in protected areas (Chernye Zemli Reserve in the Republic of Kalmykia and the Stepnoy Zakaznik in Astrakhan province) or near them, in an area of about 2–3,000 km². However, the improvement in the sex and age structure of the population observed in recent years may just suggest the end of this long period of population depression.

According to the objectives of the Saiga Conservation Strategy in the Russian Federation (sudact.ru/law/rasporiazhenie-minprirody-rossii-ot-11082021-n-30-r/prilozhenie/5), by 2030, the number of saigas in the region could increase to 20,000, and their range may grow to 20,000 km². Basically, this will involve the eastern districts of the Republic of Kalmykia (Chernozemelsky, Yustinsky and

Yashkul'sky Districts), whose rangelands, according to astrastat.gks.ru, were grazed by 1,328,300 sheep and goats as of 2019 – saigas' main competitors for food.

In 2021, WWF allocated us a grant to study the current state of rangelands and to make a vegetation map (scale 1:200,000) of the territory of the current and expected distribution of the

north-west pre-Caspian saiga population. Field studies were conducted within the supposed area of distribution in 2021–2022. Information was collected on transects with a total length of 4,300 km. The transect surveys resulted in 142 geobotanical descriptions, 23 geobotanical profiles and 4 soil profile descriptions, about 600 herbarium sheets and more than 6,000 photographs. Changes in vegetation were recorded with the help of an odometer on a topographic map with a scale of 1:100,000.

Subsequent analysis of the data using cartographic sources and remote sensing results, including Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellite images, made it possible to create a vector map of the current vegetation in the area using ArcGIS software. The map consists of the following layers: vegetation contours with an attribute table, the border between the desert and steppe zones, fallows, fields, sors (flat salt-pan depressions, with the surface covered with a white salt crust in the dry season), loose sands, lakes, irrigation canals, human settlements and paved roads.

Fig. 1. *Salsola tragus* on the sands. Photo by I. Safronova

Fig. 2. *Artemisia lerchiana*-*Poa bulbosa* deserts. Photo by I. Safronova

Fig. 3. Saiga records in 2021 and 2022

Legend

Authors' observations:

- 1 – May-June 2021
- 2 – August 2021
- 3 – May 2022

Interviews with farmers:

- 4 – observed in 2021
- 5 – observed in 2021 and 2022
- 6 – not observed for a long time
- 7 – pastures fenced with 'electric shepherds'

The map legend contains descriptions of 61 vegetation communities, of which 16 are located in the steppe and 45 in the desert zones. The spatial structure of the vegetation is mostly heterogeneous. Each vegetation community profile includes characteristics of the dominant vegetation and elements of micro- and nano-relief near sheepfolds and wells.

A large portion of the study area is occupied by sands. Overgrazing on the sands leads both to the spread of the annual plant *Salsola tragus*, which can be eaten by saigas for a short period at certain times of year (Fig. 1), as well as to a complete disappearance of other vegetation and the formation of loose sands. Such areas are unfavourable saiga habitat. Poor-condition

vegetation was recorded in much of the Kharbinsky Reserve and to its east, between the villages of Bergin and Smushkovoye, and in the southern part of the region. However, in general, plant communities in much of the study area are in fairly good condition (Fig. 2).

Currently, saigas stay mainly within the desert zone (Fig. 3). During our field research, we encountered 1,097 saiga individuals (in May-June 2021 – 634, in August 2021 – 430, in May 2022 – 33), mainly in protected areas (Chernye Zemli Reserve and Stepnoy Zakaznik) and adjacent territories. In June 2021, we observed 3 saigas (2 females and 1 male) killed by wolves within the protected areas.

Where possible, local people were interviewed. In 2021, we interviewed 17 farmers and in 2022 12 farmers. Most of them (10 in 2021 and 7 in 2022) had not encountered saigas in the last 5–10 years (sometimes longer). However, farmers neighbouring protected areas see small groups of saigas from time to time (Fig. 3). The older generation has warm memories of the 1980s, when saigas were numerous. The most remote farms where saiga records were made in recent years include those near the villages of Chkalovsky (1 male) and Yusta (16 individuals – males, females and young), where animals were seen in May 2021, and farms located 12 km south-west of the village of Pervomaysky (2 individuals) and 16 km west of the village

Fig. 4. 'Electronic shepherd' (electric fence). Photo by I. Safronova

of Shorv (30 individuals), where saigas were recorded in summer. About 100 saigas were observed near Beloozerny village in July 2021. One farmer based to the west of the Adyk-Komsomolsky road spoke of a family of saigas that had been using the area as a calving ground for quite a long time – this year there were 10 individuals.

Recently, saiga migration in Kalmykia has been obstructed by a device known as 'electric shepherds' (fences composed of several rows of live wire to prevent the movement of livestock) (Fig. 4). So far, the largest fenced areas

in the western part of Kalmykia – on the Ergeni hill and along major roads (Fig. 3), but many farmers in the central part of the Republic also plan to install electric fences. Their number has increased in the south of the region near the village of Achinery in Chernozemelsky District. We came across fenced pastures near the protected areas along the Adyk-Yashkul and Yashkul-Utta roads. Some farmers in these areas are aware of the harm they can cause to saigas during migration and have a negative attitude to the installation of the 'electric shepherds'. Another pressing problem is the lack of watering holes for saigas.

The materials we obtained suggest that plant communities in much of the study area are in fairly good condition. Their diversity is sufficient to provide food for the growing saiga population throughout the year.

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Saigas in the Mekletinsky Reserve. Photo by I. Goryaev